

Overview of the MedHopQA track at BioCreative IX: track description, participation and evaluation of systems for multi-hop medical question answering ^{*}

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Abstract

The advent of large language models (LLMs) has revolutionized Natural Language Processing (NLP), particularly question answering (QA) across domains such as biomedicine and healthcare. The MedHopQA track at BioCreative IX calls on participants to develop QA systems capable of multi-hop reasoning for complex biomedical queries. With the growing use of LLMs in these fields, it is crucial to evaluate their reasoning abilities: we must understand what knowledge LLMs possess and what techniques can improve their responses on complex, multi-hop questions rather than on simple, single-hop questions. To increase the diversity of question types, we developed a dataset of 1,000 question-answer pairs—focused on diseases, genes, and chemicals, primarily related to rare diseases—based on publicly available Wikipedia data, enabling evaluation of system performance across a wide range of biomedical QA tasks. Each question is curated by referencing two interconnected Wikipedia pages, requiring models to integrate knowledge across sources to generate accurate answers.

Participants in the MedHopQA track received each question alongside its identifier and were asked to provide: (1) a short answer of no more than three words, and (2) an optional long answer detailing the system’s reasoning.

We received 48 submissions from 13 teams worldwide for the official test phase. We also received 19 submissions in the unofficial round. Each submission underwent evaluation using Exact Match (EM), which measures strict string-to-string correspondence of the short answer, and the MedCPT score, which assesses retrieval of the correct biomedical concepts regardless of exact wording. These metrics together allow us to capture both precise answer accuracy and deeper conceptual understanding.

The highest performance achieved was an 89.30% F1 score on the MedCPT metric and an 87.30% Exact Match. This demonstrates that system-level enhancements can boost LLM performance well beyond the zero-shot baseline of 67.40% MedCPT and 60.20% EM. The MedHopQA track dataset and other challenge materials are available at (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/research/bionlp/medhopqa>) and (<https://www.codabench.org/competitions/7609/>).

This challenge demonstrated that substantial improvements in LLM short-answer responses require the integration of techniques like Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) to inject additional knowledge and boost performance substantially. We look forward to further advancements in question-answering systems—especially for complex, multi-hop queries—and invite the community to utilize the 1,000 QA pairs developed for the MedHopQA shared task at BioCreative IX.

Keywords

BioCreative IX, MedHopQA, Multi-hop Question Answering, Large Language Model Evaluation Benchmarking

1. Introduction

Biomedical question-answering (QA) systems are indispensable for navigating the surging volume of biomedical literature, enabling researchers and clinicians to extract precise insights and generate testable hypotheses at scale. Recent breakthroughs in large language models (LLMs) have driven impressive gains on factoid QA benchmarks, yet these evaluations remain largely confined to single-hop queries—questions answerable from a single sentence or isolated snippet. In contrast, real-world biomedical queries frequently demand multi-hop reasoning, requiring models to chain together multiple pieces of evidence—for example, identifying the disease caused by a mutated gene and then determining the chemical that can alleviate the symptoms based on their biological properties. Developing

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benchmarks and methods that rigorously assess and enhance multi-hop inference in biomedicine is therefore critical to advancing automated knowledge discovery.

The BioCreative workshops have long driven community progress in biomedical text mining. From its first workshop in 2004 (BioCreative I, gene/protein mention recognition and GO annotation), through BioCreative II (gene normalization), BioCreative III (PPI article classification and interaction-method extraction), BioCreative IV (chemical NER, CTD curation, GO triage), BioCreative V–VI (chemical–protein and precision-medicine relation extraction), and BioCreative VII–VIII (large-scale chemical indexing, COVID-19 topic classification, BioRED novelty annotation, SYMPTEMIST symptom mining, pediatric phenotype extraction), the workshops have continually expanded the scope and complexity of tasks. In every iteration BioCreative organizers aim to bring in new and timely real world data challenges meaningful both to the biomedical as well as clinical text mining communities and present expert curated benchmarks that continue to become standards in their respective fields.

To this end, the MedHopQA track at BioCreative IX was designed to evaluate—and ultimately spur innovation in—multi-hop reasoning for biomedical QA. Inspired by how researchers integrate findings across papers, it asks systems to synthesize information from two interconnected Wikipedia pages rather than rely on a single citation. Participants received the collection of questions and were asked to submit both a concise short answer (≤ 3 words) and, optionally, a brief explanation of their system’s reasoning chain.

The MedHopQA dataset (8) offers broad coverage of biomedical entities—ranging from diseases and genes/proteins to chemicals—by capturing multiple entity types per question. Beyond the concise question–answer pairs, it includes long-answer annotations that document the reasoning chain behind each short answer. These detailed explanations are invaluable for assessing a system’s reasoning performance, enabling researchers to scrutinize the exact steps a model takes to arrive at its answers. Together, these features make MedHopQA uniquely valuable for evaluating end-to-end inference in biomedical QA.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Dataset description

The MedHopQA dataset is a curated collection of 1000 questions and was developed over the course of 6 months. Sixteen researchers with backgrounds in medicine, biomedicine, bioinformatics, and informatics, reviewed nearly 2,000 disease-focused Wikipedia pages and related content. From each original page, the human annotators selected a new page that linked from the first one and formulated a question that could be answered by putting together the pieces of information present in both pages. For every pair of Wikipedia pages that a human reviewer linked in a question creation, we also built an AI-generated question. All questions then were distributed to the human curators for review, in such a way that they did not know whether they were human created or AI-generated. Questions that were ultimately included in the final set fulfilled these criteria: 1) pertained to medically or biomedically relevant information, i.e. were related to medical treatment, diagnosis, prognosis, disease prevention, pathophysiology, or biology. 2) were factual, i.e., did not rely on possible or probabilistic situations. 3) were unlikely to become obsolete or change in the future. 4) were related to the textual inputs of both pages, and the answer relied on both pieces of information. 5) did not have multiple conceptual answers, i.e., if the question is asking for a gene name causing a disease, only one gene can be the answer.

Questions were evaluated based on the 5 criteria listed above, and the rejected questions were re-entered into the pool for a revision opportunity. This process produced 1,637 questions, which underwent another rigorous final review for final acceptance consisting of two stages: grammar review, and conceptual review. Four annotators participated in this rigorous step, and in the end, 1000 questions were accepted for inclusion in the dataset which we call MedHopQA. For additional details to the dataset please refer to our MedHopQA corpus paper.

2.2. Track description and participation

The MedHopQA track, timeline depicted in Figure 1, was announced in March 2025, as part of BioCreative IX to be held at IJCAI 2025, and 37 worldwide teams registered to participate in the task. The data was made available from, and participation was facilitated by the CodaBench platform, where it received registrations from 42 worldwide teams, with approximately one third of the teams being new. The challenge organizers provided detailed descriptions of the evaluation methods and provided two sets of example questions and answers both at the MedHopQA website, and at the CodaBench website.

Figure 1: MedHopQA track timeline

The test phase was held between May 27, and June 1st, and all participating teams were invited to submit up to five runs (five variations of their system), and the description of each run for evaluation. Forty-eight submissions were received during this time period. Since several teams were unable to complete the data processing within the allowed timeframe, the organizers reopened the testing phase for an unofficial round between June 10 and 18, where an additional 19 submissions were received. Each team wrote a paper detailing their approaches which were peer reviewed and revised and submitted for publication in the BioCreative IX volume proceedings. The MedHopQA shared task results were presented at the BioCreative IX workshop, on August 17 and 18, 2025.

3. MedHopQA evaluation methods

One of the most challenging tasks in LLM-based systems is their evaluation. Previous evaluation approaches have relied on sentence similarity constructs that compare the LLM provided answer to the “gold” reference answer. The text comparison is reported in the form of a Rouge score, Blue score, or F-score, where the Rouge and Blue scores measure respectively the recall and precision of overlap between the terms, bigrams, or longest string overlaps between the answers, and the F-score measures the percentage of tokens that the predicted answer has in common with the “gold” answer. In the medical domain, however, it is important to pay attention to the sensitivity of the text. Consider the two distinct disease names: *Diabetes Mellitus Type 1* and *Diabetes Mellitus Type 2*. If one were to give one name as an answer when the other is required, the F-score for this situation would not reflect the gravity of the mistake. Therefore, we aimed to address this issue when designing our evaluation approach for the MedHopQA corpus. Furthermore, to be able to hold a challenge on a platform such as CodaBench, it was important to design an evaluation script that could work with minimal resources and be able to confidently automatically evaluate all the systems outputs.

We designed the string-matching approach which we called Exact Match (EM), even though it used a significant compilation of accepted synonyms for each exact answer which were compiled manually for each entry in the MedHopQA dataset. We also designed the concept-level approach, based on MedCPT, which was run locally on our servers, and the results were communicated to the track participants via email. Due to the diligence of our data annotators in compiling the list of synonyms for each MedHopQA record, the string-matching approach and the concept-level approach are compatible in their scoring behavior. As expected, the results are higher when the concept-level approach is used.

In addition, an AI-agent based approach which takes into account the submitted long answer predictions is also in the works.

The MedHopQA baseline system is a simple zero-shot simple prompt system that utilizes GPT-4o. The prompt was *“You are a helpful assistant. Please give a short concise answer for the question consisting of one word or phrase.”* The temperature of the system was set to zero, and the maximum number of tokens allowed was set to fifteen.

3.1. Submitted Systems

Nine workshop papers were accepted to the MedHopQA track. All teams submitted systems that use LLMs, and some also incorporate retrieval-augmented generation (RAG)—which combines automated question reformulation or decomposition with external evidence retrieval (from Wikipedia, PubMed, or web-search APIs) and advanced prompting techniques—to produce both concise short answers and detailed long explanations.

The DMIS Lab’s system [1] is composed of three complementary arms: the Query2Doc arm reformulates the user’s question into a medically enriched passage, retrieves the top 1,000 BM25 hits from a May 2025 Wikipedia dump, reranks those to 200 using MedCPT, then uses few-shot prompting with GPT-4o to generate answers; the Rationale arm employs GPT-o3 with chain-of-thought (CoT) prompting to break the question into subqueries, runs the same retrieval pipeline as the Query2Doc arm on each, and appends those results to the original question before passing it to GPT-4o; and the Web Search-Augmented Retrieval arm issues the question zero-shot to the Google Search API, filters and concatenates the leading web snippets into an evidence block, and sends that block to Gemini 2.5 Pro—prompted to reason step by step—to return both a concise (one-to-three-word) answer and a detailed explanation.

The UETQuintet team’s system [2] uses GPT-4o-mini to distill the question to around 50 words and an ensemble (Random Forest, XGBoost, logistic regression) to choose whether the question can be answered directly or sequentially. For direct queries, it runs Google Search (top 10–20) and a Wikipedia TF-IDF/cosine lookup (20–50 sentences), then feeds both into o3-mini to generate long and short answers (validating the short answer via the Wikipedia API). If sequential, GPT-4o-mini splits the question into sub-questions and applies the same retrieval–answering–validation loop to each in turn.

The PreceptorAI team’s system [3] begins with NLP-driven entity extraction—applying part-of-speech tagging and noun chunking to identify multi-word noun phrases while filtering out stop words and other function words. It then generates pairwise combinations of those phrases, selects the first five pairs, and queries the Wikipedia API for each to retrieve the first two to four sentences of their summaries. These excerpts are concatenated into a unified context block which, together with the original question, is passed to MedReason-8B for answer generation. If no contextual snippets are found, the system falls back to Gemini Pro 2.5.

The Fluxion team [4] evaluated Gemini 2.0 Flash and Gemini 2.5 Flash using two distinct prompts: a zero-shot CSV-formatted prompt containing only the user’s question, and a few-shot, CoT prompt that presents two fully worked examples, instructs the model to assume the role of an expert biochemist, enforces the same CSV rules, and even included a simulated kidnapping threat to ensure compliance.

The CLaC team [5] developed two systems: Agentic-Qwen-Wikipedia wraps Qwen 2.5-Coder-32B in a SmolAgents ToolCallingAgent to decompose a query into up to three keyword subqueries, fetch each via the WikipediaRetriever API, append their key facts, and synthesize them with an internal chain-of-thought into a detailed long answer and concise short answer and

LLM-Qwen-Wikipedia-PubMed uses Qwen 3-8B-AWQ to split complex questions into targeted sub-questions, extract key phrases, retrieve relevant passages from both Wikipedia and PubMed, assess whether the gathered evidence suffices to answer the main question, and finally distill each long answer into a single-term short answer using a one-shot prompt.

The Orechovi team [6] first builds a health-focused knowledge base from 225,000 Wikipedia articles, splitting each into 512-character chunks for both BM25 and dense indexing. They decompose a multi-hop query into up to four simpler sub-questions, reformulate each as a keyword phrase, then retrieve the top five BM25 hits and top five dense results per sub-question—merging and reranking them via reciprocal rank fusion. Those snippets feed an intermediate answer generator for each sub-question, and the system finally synthesizes all intermediate responses into a concise (1–3 term) short answer alongside a detailed explanation.

The LasigeBioTM pipeline [7] begins by zero-shot benchmarking Gemma-3-1B-IT and MedGemma-27B to establish baseline performance. It then employs Mistral-7B-Instruct to extract biomedical entities, queries the Mondo Disease Ontology (OWL) for each entity, and retrieves the first paragraph of each matching Wikipedia page via the Python API. These ontology and Wikipedia snippets are concatenated with the original question and fed back to Mistral to produce the final answer.

The CaresAI team [8] fine-tuned LLaMA 3 8B—unfreezing only its attention and linear layers—on the 45-question development set supplemented with BioASQ QA pairs, experimenting with three variants (short-and-long, short-only, and long-only). At inference, they prompt the best-performing fine-tuned model on the test questions, issue a secondary prompt up to three times to extract a concise short answer, and, if that fails, fall back to the original LLaMA 3 8B.

The BioHop team [9] first inputs the question into DeepSeek R1 to create an “answer plan,” flags claims needing external evidence, then reformulates those into keyword subqueries and retrieves the top N Wikipedia passages using Rag-Gym. DeepRAG applies reward-based reranking to pick the most salient snippets, which are concatenated with the original question and plan and passed back to DeepSeek’s Answer Generator to produce both long and short answers. During training, Rag-Gym uses DPO rewards to refine DeepSeek’s parameters.

3.2. Results and Discussion

Figure 2 summarizes the world-wide participating teams in the MedHopQA shared task, their institutions of affiliation, and the number of submissions each team contributed for the shared task. Each team was allowed to make a maximum of 5 submissions during the test phase. Upon reviewing the submitted results, and communicating with the teams, we noticed that some teams could benefit from additional time due to the availability of their resources. To this end, we opened another submission window, dubbed “the unofficial test phase”, and we invited all teams to submit. Upon review of these submissions, we were proved correct in our assumption, as the newly received results contained better complete data, and improved scores. The submission scores for all participants are summarized in Table 1. Table 1 also lists the baseline system, which was a zero-shot GPT-4o system, as well as the mean and median values of all official runs. The unofficial run submissions showed that the UETQuintet team scores improved respectively to 88.1, and 89.7 for string matching and concept-level evaluation. LasigeTM team’s scores demonstrated the most notable improvement to F-scores of 56.2, and 61.4 respectively for string matching and concept level evaluation. Similarly, the CaresAI team demonstrated improvement that doubled their initial scores.

Team Participation in MedHopQA at BioCreative IX

Figure 2: Team participation in MedHopQA shared task. The dark blues marks the number of runs submitted by each team during the official test phase, and the light blue shows the number of runs submitted by each team in the unofficial test phase.

Table 1

Evaluation results ranked by the F1-score of the Exact Match and MedCPT. For each team we selected their best run. The table lists the Median and Mean values of all runs (in %).

Team	Best Run #	Exact Match	Concept Level Match
DMIS Lab	2	87.3	89.3
UETQuintet*	5	83.8	86.0
Insilicom	3	80.0	83.1
PreceptorAI*	1	73.4	78.8
Nckuiirrlab	3	66.9	76.7
Fluxion	1	68.1	72.0
CLaC*	2	67.6	71.8
Baseline	-	59.1	66.3
Orekhovich	1	43.9	51.2
Biojay	1	45.8	48.8
LasigeBioTM*	4	28.3	34.2
CaresAI*	4	18.6	31.1
LaosFun*	3	26.1	29.4
BioHop	1	20.7	29.2
Median		66.9	71.8
Mean		54.65	60.1

3.3. Conclusions

The MedHopQA shared task at BioCreative IX brings the following contributions: 1. A newly, manually created resources of multi-hop questions centered on diseases, chemicals, genes, and other aspects of medical information, sources from publicly available resources. 2. A combined total of 68 submissions, each involving different models, and variations, from world-wide institutions. Winning strategies

involved the use of GPT-4o, o3-mini, Gemini 2.5 Pro, coupled with strategies such as creative query reformulation, chain-of-thought prompting, retrieval of additional information from multiple sources as well as use of a reranker. Notably, successful teams also took care to not allow the models to perform numerous API calls that rank up on cost. Successful runs involved semantic retrieval beyond NER, creative prompt engineering, model specialization and division of labor between models as well as controlled query expansion for domain corpora. The dataset will be available on CodaBench website, to further foster the development of models that can perform multi-hop reasoning.

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